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Checking the results of Qur'an's patterns (Osveh) affliction (ebtela) and their effects on people and community's behavior evolution

Marzieh Fazlinejad ^{a*}, Soheila Jalali Kondori ^b, Parvin Baharzadeh^c, Zahra Kamkar^d

^a *S Master of Qur'an sciences and Hadith and the lecturer of Islamic education courses Yasuj medical sciences university*

^b *Al-zahra university Assistant Professor*

^c *Al-zahra university Assistant professor*

^d *Master of Islamic education teaching*

Abstract

Since the modeling is one of the best educative and behavior modification methods, and observing the people who have gaited in this path successfully, leads this way to be accessible, God has addressed these patterns(osveh), so by going through this way, become practical and accessible. Following (Tassie) these patterns is the Qur'an emphasize and disclaiming (eraz) this sanity (aqtda) causes disorder in the growth and human nurture and finally oneself stupidity (sefahat)path. One of the most important aspects of following these patterns, is following the behavior and its proudness method in affliction (ebtela). The constructive and evolutionary effect of the patterns affliction can be considered in two parts: 1-the personal effects of affliction on self-pattern existence 2-the social effects of patterns affliction [the ability to take lesson and mental health] which causes the patterns to be models and directs the society to its proper growth. "Spiritual promotion" is one of the personal effects of patterns affliction which result is that the patterns reach to their human evolution culmination in an ascending chain. Accordingly, also the believers (Momin) lead to this human evolution much lower by following the patterns .this human promotion accelerates the society growth and evolution and by executing divine traditions, ideal and idealistic society purposes come true. The most important social effects of patterns affliction is the believers "ability to take lesson" and spiritual promotion simplification and acceleration and also the society people behavior evolution that finally causes the society "mental health".

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1. Introduction

The Glorious God has provided humanity with the required means to striving towards perfection, of which exemplary models are one. The mere existence of such perfect human beings precludes the idea that religious teachings and goals are unreachable ideals. Once one observes fellow humans who have reached the zenith of excellence, s/he will ponder the possibility of following those models so that s/he may reach the same level of excellence. Although different in degrees of excellence, all exemplary models are pioneers who have embraced hardships and endured on the righteous path.

* Corresponding Author name.

2. Exemplary Models' Different Levels of Excellence

What all models share is that they have illustrated the possibility of perfection for those who desire such progress [1]. Though all share the upholding of Truth, these exemplary models, who are more often than not the same known Messengers, have nevertheless reached varying levels of excellence [2, 3].

Suffering as test apply to all human beings, and exemplary models are no exception in this regard, who have experienced the same consequences as do other people of suffering. It is arguable that the differing degrees of excellence among Messengers and other models have to do with the varying degrees of suffering that each was exposed to and how well each passed the tests. These suffering bring them good both now and in the hereafter; as a matter of fact, certain individuals have advanced to the level of Imams and Leaders after they successfully passed particular tests and suffering [4].

3. The Effects of Exemplary Models' Suffering

The constructive and evolutionary effect of the models' suffering can be divided up to two different parts:

- The effects that suffering has left on the models themselves. Such effects contribute to individual progress towards excellence and perfection.
- The effects that suffering has had for the followers of the models in the society. These effects will be covered below under "Social Effects."

It is worth noting that the majority of the effects belonging to the former group can also indirectly play a role in the effects of the latter group. These are in fact points which individual models and societies intersect at and both benefit from on their way toward perfection.

3. The Private Effects of the Models' Suffering

The most important private effect of models' suffering is the consequent persistence and perseverance they show towards "spiritual progress."The Benefactor and wicked differentiation

4. Spiritual Progress

"Progress," lexically speaking, refers to advancement towards a higher destination in small steps [5]. With this in mind, spiritual progress can thus be defined as those human activities that aim at long-term success through God's consent [6] and at achieving spiritual gain. In dealing with their spiritual side, humans need such organization and increased capability. This move or spiritual progress can only be achieved by following the guidelines provided by the Holy Koran, that is, by following the sunna (of the Messengers) humans may reach security and happiness. Conversely, lack of following these guidelines can only bring humans sorrow [7]. Only the injudicious and the foolish shall fail to follow the path [8].

One way that exemplary models spiritually progress is by mean of close rapport with God, which cannot be achieved except with a deep understanding and knowledge of God. If human beings do not find a way to connect with their creator and to be intimate with Him, they will be entrenched in internal conflicts and disorganization in life. Suffering, for believers and for the perceptive, is a very effective means to build up the said rapport and progress to higher levels for their good nature helps them constantly try to get to know God better and use this suffering to that end, always striving to get closer to Him. This is spiritual progress [9].

In this way, Koranic models and their followers get closer and closer to their ultimate end and at the same time add to their spiritual assets. In order to be placed in this rising path of spiritual progress, believers must be equipped with certain qualities that would help them pass these tests successfully. This is what separates them from the worldly people and gives them their relatively greater spirituality.piritual Progress

5. Factors and Means of Spiritual Progress

The following factors and means can be regarded as the infrastructure of that superstructure that is spiritual progress: repentance, abstinence from the execrable, consent, thankfulness, and submission,

Repentance, Penitence, and the Avoiding of Negligence In the eyes of believers close to God, due to their abundance of positive qualities and excellence, any committing of the execrable or even little diversion in attention from God are deadly sins and, upon possibly doing such things, they repent and go back to God [10]. The right way to be God's true subject is not too different: one must remain constantly in the protection of God, for a moment of inattentiveness would result in sinfulness and God's rage. Such a person must constantly implore God not to let him or her lapse or sin and keep him or her under His constant vigilance [11]. The Holy Koran call such people by the name *awab* which is the superlative form of the root *owb*, meaning a return [12]. The derivative word indicates the possibly unlimited number of times a subject can repent and return to God [13]. *Anabeh* also means the same and is derived from *nowb*, meaning repeated return [14]. In Chapter "Sad," God mentions those believers who are always endangered by anguish and distress but never fail to turn to God (e.g. David) [15]. God put David to test so that the result was David's hearing only one side of the argument and not the other one and making a judgment. Although the judgment was fair, it did not meet the requirements for a fair judgment, which David was quick to realize. To compensate for the negligence in case of an obligation, he asked for forgiveness. God, in turn, forgave him and made him His deputy on Earth [16, 17, 18].

Another exemplary model with heartily repentance is Noah. Chapter "Hood" (36-49) narrates the story of his son's sinking. The verses depict Noah as confiding in God, which although does not necessarily make him susceptible to sinfulness, does suggest the guilt he feels for someone of his flesh and blood was among the wrongdoers. Noah, subsequently, repents [19]. This repentance also makes God much more generous towards him. Noah penitence in this case serves as an example of clinging to the last rays of hope to avoid and dodge possible evil [20, 21].

In David's view, a summary trial was a kind of inattention with regard to God, even if the summary trial did justice. He thus compensates for it by penitence. This ensure his return to and constant following of the righteous path [22].

This kind of negligence can be seen in a somewhat different form in the followers and believers. Negligence here sometime equals sin vs. innocence. In such cases believers, to preclude a fall in their spiritually, must avoid sin and, should it happen, try to compensate for it so that they will not fall out of the group of spiritual humans. e, Penitence, and the Avoiding of Negligence.

6. Hopefulness and the Avoiding of the Execrable

Humans normally face many different situations in their lives which might get on the way of their goals and desires. S/he thus shall inevitably face certain wretchedness and might be torn by internal and psychological conflict so much so that non-believers might feel absurd and lost. This lack of motivation can become hopelessness and desperateness followed by depression or other mental disorders. A true believer, in contrast, would never feel such desperateness. According to Koranic thought, since God is the grand cause of all causes, he can always be turned to for assistance and guidance; this is why believers are forbidden to lose hope [23]. The most obvious of all examples where hope dominated is perhaps Zechariah who was deprived of the primary need to procreate (since he saw neither himself nor his wife potent) [24, 25]; Zechariah, nonetheless, would never give up and always pray to God regarding this problem [26].

The second most prominent example must be Jacob who had not heard of his son for years, yet did not lose hope and kept advising his sons to be heedful of God's grace [27].

Job's story is also an example of salvation after much suffering. In the face of all the suffering he faced, Job never lost hope [28] and thus God opened up promising perspectives before him [29]. In the three first stories of suffering, all the usual means and ways were literally blocked [30]; but neither lost hope, knowing sin is like a blind surrounds

the heart and prevents human perfection and spiritual progress. This is why when all was more than ready for them to lose hope, they never did; in fact, they all kept praying to God (as an educational factor).

7. Thankfulness

Solomon was a messenger exposed to much bliss as well as suffering and test. When all was well, he would thank God verbally as well as non-verbally for he, as the leader whom people followed, knew that thankfulness showed wisdom and acknowledgment of both God and His gifts. This kind of understanding is not available except to spiritually mature and maturing people. With this thankfulness, Solomon was actually starting out on the way to human perfection and spiritual progress.

This type of thankfulness and acknowledgment before the gift giver also brought Ibrahim and his son's a lot of grace and gift [31]. Of the many positive outcomes were the righteous offspring that were bestowed upon him out of whom came the Last Messenger, Muhammad (pbuh) [32].

The Holy Koran views Lot's and his daughters' redemption from the most depraved place on Earth as the answer to his thankfulness and submission [33].

In order to be truly thankful, first and foremost, one must know that God's gifts and bliss are so excessive that s/he cannot possibly thank Him enough. Admitting this inability is enough to partially compensate for it. Second, "narrating the bliss" [tahdis-e ne'mat] is another way to be thankful. Generous people, once some luxury comes their way, speak of it and thank God for it. This is in sharp contrast to the envious who is always complaining and insists on denying or hiding God's gifts and whose facial expression and speech always indicates poverty [35]. The thankful person constantly notices whatever God provides him with and this facilitates his/her ascent in spiritual progress.

8. Trust in God

In Islamic thought, *tavakkol* or Trust in God refers to the belief in God as a most reliable source in the case of any possible hardship that may or may not come our way [36]. Human's Trust in God results from the acknowledgment of God's being the only and the one God. Full of miseries and suffering, exemplary models' life would not have been the same in terms of spiritual progress had it not been filled with suffering. Trust in God, consequently, must have always had high priority in their plans and lives.

Koranic examples, staunch in their belief that it is impossible for God to betray His subjects, would not consider any reason strong enough not to have one's full, unconditional Trust in God. In hardship, agony, and abuse they would persevere and would not fear harm or loss. This forms the basis of the practice that makes these models secure in the face of any suffering and distress [37].

Of the exemplary models showing unrivaled Trust in God is Ibrahim, who the pagans decided to set on fire [38]. No sooner than was Ibrahim in the fire than God commanded the fire be ineffective [39]. He who chooses God as the source of reliance shall be accompanied by Him in miseries and difficulties [40]. The Messengers were perfect examples of Trust in God, which was perhaps of the primary reasons they were so dear to God [41].

10. Consent

"Consent" [42] literally means lack of negative response to God's plans [43]. A subject's consent towards God, or more precisely towards whatever that God may want for him/her does not only mean not being unhappy but actually being happy and satisfied. This is possible when a subject submits to predestination and God's judgment [44]. True believers are truly happy with what God has in reserve for them and believe that this is the best in God's judgment. It is said that Imam Moses asked God, "who are you most unhappy with?" and God answered "s/he who wants me to do him/her good, but once I grant him/her that becomes angry with my judgment." Imam's follow up question was

about who God was happy with to which the response was “a subject who does not become angry at me even if their beloved is taken away from the” [45].

Consent to God’s plan is a practice shared by all the Koranic examples, the most obvious of which is perhaps Noah’s suffering [46]. If God makes a subject deal with hardships, it is not because he has some problem with the subject, but conversely because He judges the subject’s good being in that event at the moment.

9. Submission

Indicates a subjects being redeemed of any flaw or fault and its being purified. Submission is a situation in which the owned is readily at the service of the owner. In this state, the person’s whole existence becomes filled with belief and certainty that no cause has any effect except if willed by God. As a result, the person is always satisfied with what God plans for him/her, will not be depressed by any undesirable happening and will not fear any problem [48]. Koranic examples all show submission as a definitive characteristic. The very letter of the Holy Koran emphasizes the quality of submission in Ibrahim [49].

In the sacrifice suffering, Ibrahim was not the only one to show submission—Ismail also showed great submission, so both of the two heroes submitted to God’s will: the father to sacrifice and the son to be sacrificed.

Ibrahim’s and Jacob’s final words to their children were “do not leave the world unless with a heart filled with belief and submission” [50]. Submission of this kind but of lower levels can be Queen Saba’s which shows how to follow the examples.

10. The Levels and Degrees of Spiritual Progress

To spiritually progress, one has to follow. Following the practice of the exemplary models can teach us how to act in the face of problems and distress and passes along generations their experiences. As examples are from different levels and degrees, their spirituality is also marked by various levels and degrees, of which the following stand out.

11. Estefa

Estefa can be defined as separating the pure [51] from the impure, meaning “a self’s being healthy and clean from impurity and malevolence” [52]. Sometimes it can mean participating in activities in which others do not. Therefore, the estefa of Adam means that he was the “first” creature of the kind to reside on earth and to have repentance as an option [53]; the first order of these characteristics was given to Adam and led to his superiority against others. Noah was also the first messenger of a religion with scripture [54].

Narratives tell the story in this way: “When God loves a subject, He shall put him/her to test; when He waits, the subject shall be chosen; and, when He is satisfied, He purifies the subject” [55].

Mustafa is a perfect human being, superior to all since he is the representative of morality and spirituality. A person’s degree of estefa differs with his/her degree as an individual. The Holy Mary and Jesus Christ were of this order, and the Islamic Messenger Muhammad was at the peak [56].

12. Epiphany and Revelation

Epiphany is a sudden realization that an individual gains without learning or training, which is experienced differently by people from different spiritual levels [57]. In other words, these are the sources of actions that guarantee the best results both here and now and in the afterlife. Epiphany has many different levels. Imam Moses has received different levels of sudden knowledge, some higher and more important than others, at a number of times. Imam Moses through good deed and acts of generosity reached this high level of spirituality. Of these epiphanies, one took place before the return to Egypt, one after Pharaoh sank, and yet another at the time of the revelation of the Old Testament. Although all were true in the same sense, but they happened one at a time and progressively [58].

In such manner was it that different levels of suffering brought Moses different levels of revelation. Ibrahim, himself granted revelatory knowledge, asked God for more of this uncanny experience. [59]. Revelation and good deed are not easy to classify—that is why Ibrahim had to actually ask God for higher levels of this gift. Also, from the high level of spirituality that he was, Ibrahim would still desire to be cleaner and better than ever [60, 61].

These two godly gifts were granted Joseph because of his virtue, piety, patience, and Trust in God [62]. Certain interpreters have argued that the Mohsenin are the same as those with high patience in cases of suffering [63]. Thus it may be concluded that this gift was not given to him from the outset but was rather granted him after his endurance in the face of suffering.

14. Veracity and Oratory

The terms, standing for *sharh-e sadr*, indicate the God-given gift to receive and convey whatever meaning [64]. This concept is the most important one in understanding highly difficult holy meanings. This gift, the ability to accept difficulties, suffering, and abusive speech is the same quality Moses felt required and asked God to give him in order to be able to speak before Pharaoh who claimed to be God. It is worth noting that this gift (and mission) was given to Moses after he had successfully passed much suffering [65]. Veracity, oratory, and Trust in God enabled Moses to challenge Pharaoh and stand his derogatory comments. Another topnotch example of this gift is the Messenger of Islam (pbuh). His lifestyle both in times of difficulty and ease may be the best source of enlightenment for those who seek to follow him. His prophetic career was all an example of perseverance in the face of hardships which led to the beautiful result of veracity and oratory. The suffering that he went through as a child such as being fatherless and homeless and poverty put him to enough test [66]. After successfully coming out of these sufferings, he was granted material gifts. All these went into the making of a background on which to appear spiritual and heavenly gifts, amongst which veracity and oratory so much so that he became God's confidant [67].

13. Being Chosen

Once God wills, He will grant one generosity and grandeur so that s/he will not be lost among worldly issues, which is achieved by God's choosing certain ways and activities for the person and becoming his guide—this is called being chosen [*ejteba*]. The concept has been at times employed in the Holy Koran with regard to a set of Messengers with no apparent reason [68] and at times with reference to a specific Messenger with a specific reason [69].

In public verses around the concept, being chosen is mentioned after naming a few Messengers. A different set of verses around the concept have discussed being chosen with regard to four holy figures: 1. Adam's being chosen after he was exiled from the Garden of Eden and repented. These verses mention being chosen as a result of repentance after narrating his suffering [70].

2. Jonah's being chosen after he was eaten up by a whale. The verses talk about God's gift after the sufferings. The word *ne'mat* in this verse means repentance, meaning that had Jonah not received the gift of repentance from God and had not compensated for all that he had neglected [72], he would have been left alone in the desert. Although disregard for religious obligations normally warrants reproach, a gift from God did not let that happen. Not only was Jonah not reproached, but God actually chose him and put him among the righteous.

3. By telling his father about his dream, Joseph gave a clear spiritual image of the future. With his spiritual position and holy spirit, Jacob did anticipate the bad events that were to happen to Joseph but did not let Joseph know about them, which is itself a sign of a test which he knew would lead to his son's being chosen.

4. Ibrahim's being chosen after the sufferings. Of the prominent characteristics of Ibrahim was thankfulness for every little or big gift he received from God. This led to God's keeping him dear as well, so that he was chosen as God's Confidant [*Khalil al-lah*], God immediately uses the word being chosen [*ejteba*] after the descriptions of Ibrahim's thankfulness, suggesting that must have been the reason.

14. Imamate and Leadership

Imam is one whom others can turn to in cases of spiritual and mystical needs and religious obligations [75]. He is the connection between God and people for the granting of spiritual degrees. [76]. The Holy Koran sees the holy gifts after relating the stories of Loot's and Ibrahim's predicament in those two pieces of lands and then their salvation as the rewards of spiritual progress; all in all, such cases clearly illustrate that reaching such high spiritual positions were the outcomes of successfully passing God's tests of suffering [77]. The Imamate of Ibrahim was granted him after a series of suffering from which he had come out proud [78].

Last words: it means putting an end to a series of changes and sufferings so that certain changes appear in the spiritual life followed by perfection in attentiveness and communication. Only then is one ready to take the responsibility of Imamate [79].

Where there is suffering and tests, there is room for patience to show itself. Thus, this important means of spiritual progress is the single most effective means that opened the eyes of these models to the truth and helped them easily ascend the spiritual ladder.

15. The Social Effects of Suffering

One main shared goal of the Messengers was to provide people with social and political freedom. The difference between the Messengers' religions and human-rooted worldly religions is that the former aims at spiritual freedom as well as social freedom; without the former the latter is only a myth [80]. This kind of freedom is what is called by religious terminology "self-purification" and "piety" that frees human beings from the chokes of egoistic selves.

One of the main aspects of following in the path of the exemplary models is to achieve spiritual freedom to be followed by social freedom; these models serve as examples in cases of (social) hardship and as sources of good in conducive times. These same models usually become the symbol of and defender of people's rights in social movements [81]. The following two groups can be identified as the most important effects of the exemplary models' suffering:

16-1. *Providing examples and facilitating believers' move towards perfection*

"Learning from an example" means to form conclusions [82]. The Holy Koran has defined holy practices and has urged all to follow them so the way to perfection might be facilitated for human beings. Of the main foundations of learning from examples are getting to know honors and right ways, putting trust in God, and avoiding doubts so that the latter may not slow down humans' move to perfection. Messengers and great leaders as well as exemplary models reveal such practices so to encourage learning from examples in the domains of thought [83]. They are like roads [84] flattened by hardships and suffering ready for those who want to move fast towards perfection. They have either removed or belittled the blockades so that believers may not be misled or stopped but rather encouraged to employ examples and experiences to fight possible fears. The Holy Koran narrates the life-story of Messengers who overcame burdens [85] and invites believers to follow in the path of these examples [86]. In fact, by telling the stories of these practices and life-stories, God is saying to believers that they are not alone in suffering, but rather the best of people have had similar difficulties [87].

16-2. *Social Mental Health*

The evolutionary approach taken by Islam emphasizes the progression of the individual to be followed by the society. To unite a nation, Islam upholds the shared objective of true happiness and closeness to God. The most lasting effect a person may have on a society (and on the individuals therein) is to improve the worldview, value systems, or beliefs of a society. The effect the Messengers have had on societies are of this kind, which the Holy Koran describes as :
AL-FATH (VICTORY)(29):

« كَزُرْعٍ أَخْرَجَ شَطْهُ فَازَرَهُ فَاسْتَغْلَظَ فَاسْتَوَى عَلَى سُوْقِهِ يُعْجِبُ الزُّرَّاعَ لِيَغِيظَ بِهِمُ الْكُفَّارَ »

Muhammad is the Messenger of God; and those who are with him are strong against Unbelievers, (but) compassionate amongst each other. Thou wilt see them bow and prostrate themselves (in prayer), seeking Grace from God and (His)

Good Pleasure. On their faces are their marks, (being) the traces of their prostration. This is their similitude in the Torah; and their similitude in the Gospel is: like a seed which sends forth its blade, then makes it strong; it then becomes thick, and it stands on its own stem, (filling) the sowers with wonder and delight. As a result, it fills the Unbelievers with rage at him. God has promised those among them who believe and do righteous deeds Forgiveness, and a great Reward. (48:29)

The verse with the description of the prophet and his followers states the deep influence of a good leader on the communal spirit and objectives that a nation or society is striving towards [88].

Jonah's tribe by turning suffering into bliss are an example of such a society and such a leader. Conversely, nations such as those of Noah's, Ad's, Hood's, Samood's, and others' did not manage to do so and thus fell under the rage of God and perished.

16. Conclusion

God has provided humans with certain means to move towards self-betterment and perfection. exemplary models are one main such means, who have themselves paved the way and invite and encourage others only to follow in their path. One of the main aspects of following examples is to follow and imitate how proudly and successfully they reacted to suffering. The constructive and evolutionary role of the sufferings experienced by models can be put into two main categories:

17-1. The effects that suffering has left on the models themselves. Such effects contribute to individual progress towards excellence and perfection.

17-2. The effects that suffering has had for the followers of the models in the society. These effects were referred to above as "Social Effects."

The most important of individual effects is spiritual progress and advancement, while the most influential of all social effects seems to be the contribution to a society's spiritual adjustment and eventually its mental health.

Footnotes:

1-Abbasi moghaddam, Mostafa, patterns role in promoting and nurturer, p165.

2- Al-BAQARA(the Cow): 253, « *تِلْكَ الرُّسُلُ فَضَّلْنَا بَعْضَهُمْ عَلَى بَعْضٍ مِنْهُمْ مَنْ كَلَّمَ اللَّهُ وَ رَفَعَ بَعْضَهُمْ دَرَجَاتٍ* ». those messengers we endowed with gifts, some above others: to one of them allah spoke; others he raised to degrees (of honour); to Jesus the son of mary we gave clear (signs), and strengthened him with the holy spirit. if Allah had so willed, succeeding generations would not have fought among each other, after clear (signs) had come to them, but they (chose) to wrangle, some believing and others rejecting. if Allah had so willed, they would not have fought each other; but Allah fulfilled his plan.

3- Modaresi, Mohammad Taghi, guidance interpretation, vol 6, p 246.

4 - Al-BAQARA: 124, « *وَ إِذِ ابْتَلَىٰ إِبْرَاهِيمَ رَبُّهُ بِكَلِمَاتٍ فَأَتَمَّهُنَّ قَالَ إِنِّي جَاعِلُكَ لِلنَّاسِ إِمَامًا* ». and remember that abraham was tried by his lord with certain commands, which he fulfilled: he said: "i will make thee an imam to the nations." he pleaded: "and also (imams) from my offspring!" he answered: "but my promise is not within the reach of evil-doers.

5 - Ragheb Esfahani, Hossein ibn Muhammad al-mofradat fi gharib al-Qur'an, vol 1, p 363.

6 - Lamei, Abulfath, the quality Management Principles, p. 21.

7 - Nejati, Mohammad Usman, Quran and Psychology, p. 374.

8 - Al-Baqarah: 130: « *وَ مَنْ يَرْغَبْ عَنْ مِلَّةِ إِبْرَاهِيمَ إِلَّا مَنْ سَفِهَ نَفْسَهُ* ». and who turns away from the religion of abraham but such as debase their souls with folly? him we chose and rendered pure in this world: and he will be in the hereafter in the ranks of the righteous

- 9 - Abbasnejad, Mohsen., *Psychology and Educational Sciences*, page 89.
- 10 - Hussaini shah, Abdul-azimi, Hussein bin Ahmad, *the interpreting Asna Ashari*, vol 6, p 78.
- 11 - Hussein Hamadani , Mohammad. Hussain , *Anware derakhshan(the bright lights)* , vol 8 , p 415.
- 12 - Raghieb Isfahani, Husayn ibn Muhammad, *al- mufradat fi qarib al-Qur'ant*, vol 1 , p 363.
- 13 - Tabatabaei , Seyed Mohammad Hussein , *Al-mizan fi tafsir al-Qur'an*, vol 17 , 189 -190 .
- 14 - Raghieb Isfahani, Husayn ibn Muhammad , , *al- mufradat fi qarib al-Qur'ant* , vol 1 , p 827 .
- 15 - SAD (THE LETTER SAD) : 17 , « *هُوَ أَذْكَرُ عَبْدَنَا دَاوُدَ ذَا الْأَيْدِ إِنَّهُ أَوَّابٌ* » , and remember our servant david, the man of strength: for he ever turned (to allah).
- 16 - SAD (THE LETTER SAD) : 25-26 « *يَا دَاوُدُ إِنَّا جَعَلْنَاكَ خَلِيفَةً فِي الْأَرْضِ فَاحْكُم بَيْنَ النَّاسِ بِالْحَقِّ* » (so we forgave him this (lapse): he enjoyed, indeed, a near approach to us, and a beautiful place of (final) return. o david! we did indeed make thee a vicegerent on earth: so judge thou between men in truth (and justice): nor follow thou the lusts (of thy heart), for they will mislead thee from the path of allah: for those who wander astray from the path of allah, is a penalty grievous, for that they forget the day of account)
- 17 - Tabatabaei , Seyed Mohammad Hussein , *al-mizan fi tafsir al-Qura'n* , vol 17 , p 188.
- 18 – the second Awab servant who is recalled in this chapter , is Solomon - peace be upon him - that God laid a dead body on his bed to examine him . So he turned to the Lord SAD (THE LETTER SAD) : 30-34 ; the third recalled pattern of Awwabin group in this chapter is Ayub –PBUH- him – whose story is told by God, SAD (THE LETTER SAD) : 44 , « *إِنَّا وَجَدْنَاهُ صَابِرًا نَعْمَ الْعَبْدُ إِنَّهُ أَوَّابٌ* » , "and take in thy hand a little grass, and strike therewith: and break not (thy oath)." truly we found him full of patience and constancy. how excellent in our service! ever did he turn (to us)!"
- 19 - Najafi Khomeini, Mohammad Javad,(Tafsire asan) easy to interpret , vol 7 , p 296.
- 20 –different examples of this neglect return and avoidance can be seen in Qur'an such as: AL-ARAF (THE HEIGHTS) : 143 , Musa –PBUH- Repentance(towbeh) about being on behalf of Bani esrael(the children of Israel) displaced demand about visiting God; HUD (HUD)(75) Ibrahim-PBUH- return in God debate story about Lot people rescue of imminent doom; AL-ANBIYA (THE PROPHETS),(87) Jonah –PBUH- repentance because of prematurely leaving of his people; AL-BAQARA(the cow) 37: Adam –PBUH- repentance after eating forbidden fruit; Imam Sadiq-PBUH- narration says: « *ان رسول الله- صلي الله عليه وآله- كان يتوب الي الله في كل يوم سبعين مره من غير ذنب* » , "that the Messenger of Allah - peace be upon him and his family - he has to repent to God every day seventy times of non-guilt", Bahri, Seyyed Hashem, *Al-bohran fi tafsir al-Qur'an*, vol5, p 64.
- 21 - Tusi, Muhammad ibn Hasan , *Altabyan fi tafsir al-Qur'an*, vol 5 , p 496.
- 22 - on the other patterns(Osveh) also the process is the same as saying " God willing "(En sha Allah), in the words of Solomon , Satan temptation against Prophet Ayub [even though he has not paid attention, the mind imaginative of Noah [although he has not say it] ... and all of these cases, is the neglect and exclusion from the constant presence of God's presence and the absence of presence is reducing the spirituality that must be compensated with return and Anabeh(repentance) .
- 23 - AZ-ZUMAR (THE TROOPS)53 « *لَا تَقْنَطُوا مِنْ رَحْمَةِ اللَّهِ* ».(despair not of the mercy of allah)
- 24 - MARYAM (MARY) (8) « *فَدَّ بَلَغْتُ مِنَ الْكِبَرِ عِتِيًّا* ».(when my wife is barren and i have grown quite decrepit from old age?)
- 25 - AL-E-IMRAN (THE FAMILY OF 'IMRAN)(40) « *هُوَ أَمْرَأَتِي عَاقِرٌ* ».(and my wife is barren?" "thus," was the answer, "doth allah accomplish what he willeth.)
- 26 - MARYAM (MARY)(4): « *قَالَ رَبِّ إِنِّي وَهَنَ الْعَظْمُ مِنِّي وَاسْتَعَلَ الرَّأْسُ شَيْبًا وَلَمْ أَكُنْ بِدُعَائِكَ رَبِّ شَقِيًّا* » .praying: "o my lord! infirm indeed are my bones, and the hair of my head doth glisten with grey: but never am i unblest, o my lord, in my prayer to thee!
- 27 - YUSUF (JOSEPH)(27) « *يَبْنِي أَذْهَبُوا فَتَحَسَبُوا مِنْ يُوسُفَ وَأَخِيهِ وَلَا تَأْتِسُوا مِنْ رَوْحِ اللَّهِ إِنَّهُ لَا يَأْتِسُ مِنْ رَوْحِ اللَّهِ إِلَّا الْقَوْمَ الْكَافِرُونَ* » .
"but if it be that his shirt is torn from the back, then is she the liar, and he is telling the truth!"

the water abated, and the matter was ended. the ark rested on mount judi, and the word went forth: "away with those who do wrong! and noah called upon his lord, and said: "o my lord! surely my son is of my family! and thy promise is true, and thou art the justest of judges!"

47 - Mesbah Yazdi , Mohammad Taghi, the goers through God ally, p 36.

48 - YUNUS (JONAH) (62), «أَلَا إِنَّ أَوْلِيَاءَ اللَّهِ لَا خَوْفَ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا هُمْ يَحْزَنُونَ», behold! verily on the friends of allah there is no fear, nor shall they grieve.

49 - AL-BAQARA (THE COW)(130131) «وَلَقَدْ اصْطَفَيْنَاهُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَ إِنَّهُ فِي الْآخِرَةِ لَمِنَ الصَّالِحِينَ. إِذْ قَالَ لَهُ رَبُّهُ أَسْلِمْ قَالَ أَسْلَمْتُ لِرَبِّ «أَلْعَالَمِينَ» and who turns away from the religion of abraham but such as debase their souls with folly? him we chose and rendered pure in this world: and he will be in the hereafter in the ranks of the righteous.

50 - AL-BAQARA (THE COW)(132) «وَوَصَّى بِهَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ بَنِيهِ وَيَعْقُوبَ يَا بَنِي إِسْمَاعِيلَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ اصْطَفَى لَكُمْ الدِّينَ فَلَا تَمُوتُنَّ إِلَّا وَ أَنْتُمْ مُسْلِمُونَ» and this was the legacy that abraham left to his sons, and so did jacob; "oh my sons! allah hath chosen the faith for you; then die not except in the faith of islam.

51 - Makarem Shirazi , Nasser , al-amsal fi tafsir al-ketab Allah al-manzel, vol 2 , p 471.

52 - Mostafavi , Hassan. , bright interpretation, vol 2 , p 108.

53 – dependence is a superior degree which causes opening the doors to humans . Although Adam - peace be upon him - was tempted by Satan ,by dependence and return to God compensate replaced it and this replacement was not only his pride in affliction, but also caused to his election.

54 - Tabatabai , Seyed Mohammad Hossein , Al-mizan fi tafsir al-Qur'an , vol 8 , 313.

55 – Mohammad –PBUH- said: "certainly God loves the servant who is well patient in afflictions and is satisfied of the thing that he has chosen., Mohades Noori, Hossein, Mostadrek al-vasael(the mean understanding), Al al-beit al-ahya altaras, Qom, 1408 L, vol 2, Bab estehbab al-sabr ala al-bala, p427.

56 - Mousavi Sabzwari , Abdul Aala , Mavaheb al-rahman fi tafsir al-Quran , vol 5 , p 257.

57 - Amin , Nosrat , makhzan al-erfan , vol 9 , p 255.

58 - AL-QASAS (THE STORY)(14) «هو اتيناه حكماً و علماً و كذلك نجزي المحسنين» when he reached full age, and was firmly established (in life), we bestowed on him wisdom and knowledge: for thus do we reward those who do good.

59 - AL-SHUARA (THE POETS)(83) «رَبِّ هَبْ لِي حُكْمًا وَ الْإِحْسَانَ بِالصَّالِحِينَ» "o my lord! bestow wisdom on me, and join me with the righteous.

60 - YUSUF (JOSEPH)(22) «وَأَتَيْنَاهُ حُكْمًا وَ عِلْمًا وَ كَذَلِكَ نَجْزِي الْمُحْسِنِينَ» when joseph attained his full manhood, we gave him power and knowledge: thus do we reward those who do right.

61 - Tabatabai , Seyyed Mohammad Hossein , al-mizan fi tafsir al-Quran, vol 15 , p 69.

62 - Hussein Shah, Abdul azimi - Hussein ibn Ahmad , Asna Ashari(Duodecimal) interpretation , vol 9 , p 360.

63 - Tabrasi, Fadl ibn Hassan, Majma al-bayan fi tafsir al-Quran , vol 3 , p 222.

64 - Raghil Isfahani, Hussein ibn Muhammad al- mofradat fi gharib al-Qur'an , vol 1, 449.

65 - TA-HA (TA-HA) – (24-37) «أَذْهَبْ إِلَى فِرْعَوْنَ إِنَّهُ طَغَى. قَالَ رَبِّ اشْرَحْ لِي صَدْرِي. وَ يَسِّرْ لِي أَمْرِي. وَ اخْلُقْ عُقْدَةً مِن لِسَانِي. يَتَفَهَمُوا قَوْلِي. وَ اجْعَلْ لِي وَزِيرًا مِّنْ أَهْلِي. هَارُونَ أَخِي. اشْدُدْ بِهِ أَزْرِي. وَ اشْرِكْهُ فِي أَمْرِي. كَيْ نُسَبِّحَكَ كَثِيرًا. وَ نَذْكُرَكَ كَثِيرًا. إِنَّكَ كُنْتَ بِنَا نَصِيرًا. قَالَ فَذُؤْتِي «سُؤْلَكَ يَا مُوسَى. وَ لَقَدْ مَنَّا عَلَيْكَ مَرَّةً أُخْرَى».

"go thou to pharaoh, for he has indeed transgressed all bounds. (moses) said: "o my lord! expand me my breast; "ease my task for me. "and remove the impediment from my speech, "so they may understand what i say, "and give me a minister from my family, "aaron, my brother, "add to my strength through him, "and make him share my task, "that we may celebrate thy praise without stint, "and remember thee without stint, "for thou art he that (ever) regardeth us, (allah) said: "granted is thy prayer, o mooses!", "and indeed we conferred a favour on thee another time (before)!"

66 - AD-DHUHA (THE MORNING HOURS) (6-8): «أَلَمْ يَجِدْكَ يَتِيمًا فَآوَى. وَ وَجَدَكَ ضَالًّا فَهَدَى. وَ وَجَدَكَ عَانِلًا فَأَغْنَى.» did he not find thee an orphan and give thee shelter (and care)? , and he found thee wandering, and he gave thee guidance, and he found thee in need, and made thee independent)

67 – Moddaresi, Mohammad Taghi , Man hada al-Quran , vol 18 , p 192.

68 - AL-ANAAM (CATTLE)(87) « وَ اجْتَبَيْنَاهُمْ وَ هَدَيْنَاهُمْ » (to them) and to their fathers, and progeny and brethren: we chose them, and we guided them to a straight way.

69 - AL-ANAAM (CATTLE)(87-90): « وَ اجْتَبَيْنَاهُمْ إِلَىٰ صِرَاطٍ مُسْتَقِيمٍ. ذَلِكَ هُدَىٰ اللَّهِ يَهْدِي بِهِ مَنْ يَشَاءُ مِنْ عِبَادِهِ » (to them) and to their fathers, and progeny and brethren: we chose them, and we guided them to a straight way, this is the guidance of allah: he giveth that guidance to whom he pleaseth, of his worshippers. if they were to join other gods with him, all that they did would be vain for them, these were the men to whom we gave the book, and authority, and prophethood: if these (their descendants) reject them, behold! we shall entrust their charge to a new people who reject them not, those were the (prophets) who received allah's guidance: copy the guidance they received; say: "no reward for this do i ask of you: this is no less than a message for the nations."

70 - TA-HA (TA-HA) (121-122) « وَ عَصَىٰ آدَمُ رَبَّهُ فَغَوَىٰ. ثُمَّ اجْتَبَاهُ رَبُّهُ فَتَابَ عَلَيْهِ وَ هَدَىٰ.

in the result, they both ate of the tree, and so their nakedness appeared to them: they began to sew together, for their covering, leaves from the garden: thus did adam disobey his lord, and allow himself to be seduced. but his lord chose him (for his grace): he turned to him, and gave him guidance.

71 - AL-QALAM (THE PEN) (49-50) « لَوْلَا أَنْ تَدَارَكُهُ نِعْمَةٌ مِنْ رَبِّهِ لُنُبِيَ بِالْعُرَاءِ وَ هُوَ مَذْمُومٌ. فَاجْتَبَاهُ رَبُّهُ فَجَعَلَهُ مِنَ الصَّالِحِينَ » had not grace from his lord reached him, he would indeed have been cast off on the naked shore, in disgrace,. thus did his lord choose him and make him of the company of the righteous.

72 – this divine gift, is special for prophets and some of the honest people and the Martyrs who have the same degree as the prophets who are considered by God,; Tabatabaei, Seyyed Mohammad Hossein, al-mizan fi tafsir al-Qur'an vol 19 , p 647 .

73 - YUSUF (JOSEPH)(6) « وَ كَذَلِكَ يَجْتَبِيكَ رَبُّكَ وَ يُعَلِّمُكَ مِنْ تَأْوِيلِ الْأَحَادِيثِ وَ يُؤْتِيكَ نِعْمَةً عَلَيْهِ وَ عَلَيَّ عَالٍ يَعْقُوبَ كَمَا أَتَمَّهَا عَلَىٰ أَبْنَائِكَ مِنْ « هَبْلُ إِبْرَاهِيمَ وَ إِسْحَاقَ "thus will thy lord choose thee and teach thee the interpretation of stories (and events) and perfect his favour to thee and to the posterity of jacob - even as he perfected it to thy fathers abraham and isaac aforetime! for allah is full of knowledge and wisdom."

74 - Tabatabai , Seyyed Mohammad Hossein , al-mizan fi tafsir al-Quran , vol 12 , p 53.

75 - AN-NISA (WOMEN)(73) « وَ جَعَلْنَاكُمْ أَنْعَمَ يَهْدُونَ بِأَمْرِنَا » « but if good fortune comes to you from allah, they would be sure to say - as if there had never been ties of affection between you and them - "oh! i wish i had been with them; a fine thing should i then have made of it!"

76 - Tabatabai , Seyyed Mohammad Hossein , al-mizan fi tafsir al-Qur'an vol 14 , p 3.4 .

77 AL-ANBIYA (THE PROPHETS) (71-75) « وَ نَجَّيْنَاهُ وَ لُوطًا إِلَى الْأَرْضِ الَّتِي بَارَكْنَا فِيهَا لِلْعَالَمِينَ. وَ وَهَبْنَا لَهُ إِسْحَاقَ وَ يَعْقُوبَ نَافِلَةً وَ كَلًّا » وَ جَعَلْنَا صَالِحِينَ. وَ جَعَلْنَاهُمْ أَنْعَمَ يَهْدُونَ بِأَمْرِنَا وَ أَوْحَيْنَا إِلَيْهِمْ فِعْلَ الْخَيْرَاتِ وَ إِقَامَ الصَّلَاةِ وَ آيَاتِ الزَّكَاةِ وَ كَانُوا لَنَا عِبِيدِينَ. وَ لُوطًا عَاتَيْنَاهُ حُكْمًا وَ عِلْمًا وَ «نَجَّيْنَاهُ مِنَ الْقَرْيَةِ الَّتِي كَانَتْ تَعْمَلُ الْخَبِيثَاتِ إِنَّهُمْ كَانُوا قَوْمٍ فَاسِقِينَ. وَ أَدْخَلْنَاهُ فِي رَحْمَتِنَا

but we delivered him and (his nephew) lut (and directed them) to the land which we have blessed for the nations, and we bestowed on him isaac and, as an additional gift, (a grandson), jacob, and we made righteous men of every one (of them). and we made them leaders, guiding (men) by our command, and we sent them inspiration to do good deeds, to establish regular prayers, and to practise regular charity; and they constantly served us (and us only), and to lut, too, we gave judgment and knowledge, and we saved him from the town which practised abominations: truly they were a people given to evil, a rebellious people. and we admitted him to our mercy: for he was one of the righteous)

78 - AL-BAQARA (THE COW)(124) « إِذِ ابْتَلَىٰ إِبْرَاهِيمَ رَبُّهُ بِكَلِمَاتٍ فَأَتَمَّهُنَّ قَالَ إِنِّي جَاعِلُكَ لِلنَّاسِ إِمَامًا » and remember that abraham was tried by his lord with certain commands, which he fulfilled: he said: "i will make thee an imam to the nations." he pleaded: "and also (imams) from my offspring!" he answered: "but my promise is not within the reach of evil-doers."

79 - Mostafavi , Hassan. Bright interpretation, vol 2 , p 143.

80 - Motahari , Morteza. , spiritual freedom , p 16.

- 81 - Abbas Nejad , Mohsen. , *Psychology and Educational Sciences* , vol 89 , p 117.
- 82 - Mostafavi , Hassan. *Bright interpretation*, vol 16 , p 221.
- 83 - Taleghani , Mahmoud , *the light of the Qur'an* , vol 5 , p 346.
- 84 – edification verbally means the same as it.
- 85 - Hossein Hamadani , Mohammad. Hussein , *bright lights* , vol 9 , p 149.
- 86 - YUSUF (JOSEPH)(111) «أَفْعَدَ كَأَن فِي قَصَصِهِمْ عِبْرَةً لِأُولَى الْأَلْبَابِ مَا كَانَ خَدِيدًا يُفْتَنَى وَ لَاكِن تَصَدِّقَ الَّذِي بَيْنَ يَدَيْهِ وَ تُفَصِّلُ كُلَّ شَيْءٍ وَ هُدًى وَ رَحْمَةً لِّقَوْمٍ يُؤْمِنُونَ
- there is, in their stories, instruction for men endowed with understanding. it is not a tale invented, but a confirmation of what went before it,- a detailed exposition of all things, and a guide and a mercy to any such as believe
- 87 - Makarem Shirazi , Nasser , *al-amsal fi tafsir al-ketab Allah al-manzel*, vol 3 , p 197.
- 88 - AL-NOOR (THE LIGHT)(55) « وَعَدَ اللَّهُ الَّذِينَ ءَامَنُوا مِنْكُمْ وَ عَمَلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ لَيَسْتَخْلِفَنَّهُمْ فِي الْأَرْضِ كَمَا اسْتَخْلَفَ الَّذِينَ مِنْ قَبْلِهِمْ وَ «
«لَيَمَكِّنَنَّ لَهُمْ دِينَهُمُ الَّذِي ارْتَضَى لَهُمْ وَ لَيُبَدِّلَنَّهُمْ مِنْ بَعْدِ خَوْفِهِمْ أَمْنًا يَعْبُدُونَنِي لَا يُشْرِكُونَ بِي شَيْئًا
- allah has promised, to those among you who believe and work righteous deeds, that he will, of a surety, grant them in the land, inheritance (of power), as he granted it to those before them; that he will establish in authority their religion - the one which he has chosen for them; and that he will change (their state), after the fear in which they (lived), to one of security and peace: 'they will worship me (alone) and not associate aught with me. 'if any do reject faith after this, they are rebellious and wicked
- 89 - Tabatabai , Seyed Mohammad Hossein , *al-mizan fi tafsir al-Quran* , vol 11 , p 423

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